

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP 2, Improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

D2.9 Report with publications of demonstration projects

Lead contributor	E.P. van Puijenbroek, Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb
	e.vanpujenbroek@lareb.nl
Other contributors	L. Yates; KRISP, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Institute of Genetic Medicine, Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust A Alexe; Novartis Pharma GmbH U. Winterfeld; Swiss TIS J. Richardson, UKTIS A. Oliver, UKTIS R Bromley University of Manchester Y. Geissbühler, Novartis Pharma AG

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1-0.2	22-22-2024	First draft
V1.0	12-12-2024	Final version
V1.1	9-7-2025	Minor administrative revisions

Abstract

Work Package 2 (WP2) of IMI ConcePTION focusses on sources of primary data collection, such as spontaneous reports, data collected by TIS, literature, pregnancy registries, and enhanced PV studies. The primary goal of this WP was to optimize the collection of pharmacovigilance data on reported pregnancies and enhance the sharing of data and analytical methods to more quickly and effectively assess the risks associated with medication use during pregnancy and lactation. The sub-objectives were: 1) To identify and characterize existing data sources that track medication-exposed pregnancies; 2) To develop new methods and analyses for reported pregnancies; 3) To explore and compare the effectiveness of traditional and novel data collection systems, methodological approaches, and datasets through demonstration studies using diverse data sources; and 4) To create best practice guidelines for a more timely and efficient multifaceted approach to data collection, analysis, and interpretation of reported pregnancies, aiding healthcare providers and pregnant women in evaluating the risk-benefit of medication use during pregnancy.

To achieve these objectives, several demonstration studies were conducted in this WP, divided in five tasks, for each of which demonstration studies were conducted. Aim of this report is to provide an overview of publications on the various studies conducted in WP2

Content

Document History	2
Abstract.....	3
Introduction	11
Focus of demonstration studies 1 and 2	11
Demonstration study 2.5.1: Data quality & signal detection of spontaneous data -EU PAS 38841 .	12
Research question and objectives.....	12
Substudy 1: Nature and content of Spontaneous data and literature data sources.....	13
Substudy 2a Creating and validating a dedicated assessment tool for measuring the quality of pregnancy data specifically (S2), part I, Elements to assess the quality of clinical information. ..	14
<i>Substudy 2b Creating and validating a dedicated assessment tool for measuring the quality of pregnancy data specifically, part II, validation of the clinical assessment tool</i>	15
<i>Substudy 3 Quality of Clinical Information in Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Data Sources – a contribution of the ConcePTION project</i>	16
Substudy 4 Pregnancy safety signals: regulatory decisions and implementation in daily practice	17
sub-study 5 Cluster analysis of symptoms of Neurodevelopmental Delay associated with Valproate exposure during pregnancy	18
Demonstration study 2.5.2 Primary and secondary safety data in multiple sclerosis patients -EU PAS 43370.....	19
Core data elements for pregnancy pharmacovigilance studies using primary source data collection methods: recommendations from the IMI ConcePTION project	20
Delphi method consensus on statistical analysis and reporting recommendations for single arm pregnancy medication safety studies investigating pregnancy, birth and neonatal health outcomes; a contribution from IMI-ConcePTION	21
Improving Data Collection in Pregnancy Safety Studies: Towards Standardisation of Data Elements in Pregnancy Reports from Public and Private Partners, A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project	22
Improving data harmonisation in pregnancy safety studies: evaluating the feasibility of standardised data analysis of pregnancy reports from public and private partners, a contribution from the ConcePTION project.	23
Demonstration study 2.5.3 LifeTIME study focusing on neurodevelopmental delay -EU PAS 43300-43376.....	24
Demonstration study 2.5.4 TeratoPHEN	25
Demonstration study 2.5.5 Validation of primary source pregnancy pharmacovigilance data -EU PAS 44505.....	26
Sub study 1: Validation of neurodevelopmental data	26
Meeting Abstract (4th Joint ENTIS-OTIS Conference, September 12th–15th 2024, Nyborg, Denmark) – Developing a caregiver reported questionnaire set for neurodevelopmental outcomes in school-aged children for pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance: A contribution from the ConcePTION project	26
Sub study 2: Validation of child health data	27
Study manuscript (to be submitted for peer review): Impact of sodium valproate exposure in utero on longer term health: an observational study and a contribution from the ConcePTION project	28

List of abbreviations.....	29
References	30

Introduction

Treatment during pregnancy is often needed for women with pre-existing chronic conditions such as asthma, epilepsy, cancer, multiple sclerosis (MS) and depression. In daily practice the majority of women take at least one type of medicinal product during pregnancy.¹⁻³ Unfortunately, knowledge about the safety of drugs during pregnancy is often unknown at the time of product licensure because the inclusion of pregnant women in clinical trials is considered unethical.⁴ Since limited data from studies performed pre-marketing are usually available before licensure of a medicinal product, we have to rely on post-marketing data from both primary as well as secondary data sources. With respect to the primary data, several established approaches are currently used to compile and analyse the data on the safety profile of drug use during pregnancy, including data collected by Teratology Information Services (TIS), spontaneous reports, information from literature, organised data collection programmes and registries. The IMI funded ConcePTION project aims to optimise the way drug use during pregnancy is studied.³ This is done in part by improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pharmacovigilance (PV) data, to allow for a more systematic analysis and exchange of data.

Work Package 2 (WP2) of ConcePTION focusses on sources of primary data collection, such as spontaneous reports, data collected by TIS, literature, pregnancy registries, and enhanced PV studies. The primary goal of this WP was to optimize the collection of pharmacovigilance data on reported pregnancies and enhance the sharing of data and analytical methods to more quickly and effectively assess the risks associated with medication use during pregnancy and lactation. The sub-objectives were: 1) To identify and characterize existing data sources that track medication-exposed pregnancies; 2) To develop new methods and analyses for reported pregnancies; 3) To explore and compare the effectiveness of traditional and novel data collection systems, methodological approaches, and datasets through demonstration studies using diverse data sources; and 4) To create best practice guidelines for a more timely and efficient multifaceted approach to data collection, analysis, and interpretation of reported pregnancies, aiding healthcare providers and pregnant women in evaluating the risk-benefit of medication use during pregnancy.

To achieve these objectives, several demonstration studies were conducted in this WP, divided in five tasks:

- Demonstration study 1 EU PAS 38841 Analysis and signal detection of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data in spontaneous reports, and literature, (Individual Case Safety Reports originating from published case series, non-interventional studies and patient support programmes)
- Demonstration study 2 EU PAS 43370 Primary and secondary safety data in multiple sclerosis patients
- Demonstration study 3 EU PAS 43300-43376 LifeTIME study focusing on neurodevelopmental delay
- Demonstration study 4 TeratoPHEN
- Demonstration study 5 EU PAS 44505 Validation of primary source pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

Aim of this report is to provide an overview of publications on the various studies conducted in WP2

Focus of demonstration studies 1 and 2

Part of the WP2 objectives was to develop a common data model (CDM) with a distributed data approach, allowing for one centrally defined data analysis while the data access providers maintain control of their data and their use. Whereas information from spontaneous reports and literature can already be exchanged using the ICH-E2B(R3) standard⁵, automated information exchange from other primary data collections for pregnancy (e.g. TIS, registries and enhanced PV programmes) usually is not yet possible. Following discussion among the WP2 members, it was decided to focus demonstration study 1 on spontaneous reporting systems (SRS) and literature data only.

Demonstration study 2 has focussed on the description of the other primary data sources. However, in some of the sub-studies part of Demonstration studies 1, we have focussed not only on spontaneous reports and literature data, but also the data sources of demonstration study 2 (e.g. registry data, data from TIS centres and enhanced PV programmes).

In the demonstration studies described in the protocols of demonstration study 1 and 2, special attention was paid to medicinal products registered for MS. The rationale for this is that several pregnancy registries are in place for MS, both drug-specific and disease specific and enhanced PV programme approaches are in place for several MS drugs. Focus on these drugs with the same indication would enable a better alignment of the outcomes among all data sources and studies in WP2 as well as WP1. Apart from medicinal products indicated for MS, the analyses proposed in these demonstration studies may have been extended to other medicinal products and indications when considered relevant (e.g. in the case that the power of the studies is too limited or if the generalisability is at risk).

Demonstration study 2.5.1: Data quality & signal detection of spontaneous data -EU PAS 38841

Observations from daily practice are either published in the form of case reports or submitted as (spontaneous) reports to MAHs, national PV centres and international centres like the EMA and the WHO. These observations have been proven to be a useful tool in the detection of safety information in respect to the safety of registered medicinal products used during pregnancy, but they all have their shortcomings and are also not optimized for pregnancy data.⁶⁻¹⁰ Information of spontaneous data is stored in databases in the ICH-E2B(R3) format.⁵ This format has not specifically been designed to store safety information related to pregnancy, which may have an impact on the quality of information and the way these data are analysed. As a first step, the nature and content of the currently available data in Spontaneous Reporting Systems were described. The presence and absence of data that are relevant for the analysis of exposure during pregnancy were assessed. Despite many fields available in the ICH-E2B(R3) model, it is not clear if the information is of sufficient quality to assess the causal relationship between exposure to a medicinal product during pregnancy and reported events in the mother or her (unborn) child. Existing methods to assess the quality were not designed to specifically assess the quality of pregnancy data, and are therefore not suitable for the assessment of reports regarding pregnancy.^{11 12}

Current signal detection methods are mostly focussed on associations between a medicinal product and a single adverse drug reaction (ADR) while many ICSRs report two or more ADRs.

Research question and objectives

The main objective of demonstration study 1 is to gain insight into the nature of information on drug exposure during pregnancy from spontaneous reports and literature reports.

As part of demonstration studies 1, a new dedicated model for the measurement of clinical quality of ICSRs has been developed and the quality of various primary data sources, among which spontaneous data, registry data, data from TIS centres and enhanced PV programmes, were analysed. In addition we explored the possibilities to apply cluster analysis for teratogen signal detection. The following five sub studies were conducted, with the following aims:

1. Describing the nature and content of SRS and literature data sources (**S1**)
2. Creating and validating a dedicated assessment tool for measuring the quality of pregnancy data specifically, which resulted in two separate studies. (**S2a and S2b**)
3. Describing the quality of reports in SRS, literature, TIS, registries and enhanced PV programme data (**S3**)
4. Assessing predictors of currently used teratogen signal detection in ICSR databases (**S4**)
5. Exploration of cluster analysis as a possible new teratogen signal detection technique (**S5**)

Substudy 1: Nature and content of Spontaneous data and literature data sources

1. Outcomes have been presented as a poster presentation at the 38th ICPE Copenhagen August 2022: Yrea R.J. van Rijt-Weetink, David J. Lewis, Laura M. Yates, Eugène P. van Puijenbroek. Characterization of Pregnancy Data reported by Health Care Professionals versus Patients in International Case Safety Reports – A ConcePTION Study. *Pharmacoepidemiology and Drug Safety* 2022;31(s2):260.
2. A manuscript of the findings of this study will be submitted for publication end of 2024.
3. This study has been published as a Master thesis at the University of Groningen.

Background: Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs) are an important source of information for post-marketing safety data relating to pregnancy. Since the introduction of patient reporting, several studies focused on differences and similarities between reports from Health Care Professionals (HCPs) and patients, but to our knowledge none specifically for pregnancy ICSR.

Objective: To compare the nature and completeness of ICSR relating to medicinal product exposure during pregnancy reported by HCPs versus consumers as received by the Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb.

Methods: ICSR submitted before 2022 were selected from the Lareb database when related to medicinal product exposure during pregnancy. The nature of the reports was described according to reporter, year of reporting, seriousness, medicinal product, and reported (adverse) reactions. Completeness of pregnancy related variables was described as the percentage of cases in which the variable had been reported. Completeness was assessed for variables relating to demographics, the reported reaction, the medicinal product(s), the pregnancy, the offspring, and the mother. Aggregate analyses of reports were compared between HCPs and patients using Pearson's Chi-squared test.

Results: 3478 ICSR were included, of which 74.3% reported by HCPs. A mean of 1.2 (range 1-10) medicinal products were reported per ICSR, the intrauterine device with progestogen most commonly reported (7.4% of reports). Spontaneous abortion was the most commonly reported outcome (7.3%). Completeness of the variables varied widely, from infant head circumference (0.45%) to the sex of the child (100%). Variables such as mothers' date of birth (HCP 53.5% vs. patient 76.0%, $p < 0.001$) and drug start date (HCP 45.7% vs. patient 75.1%, $p < 0.001$) were reported more by patients, while variables such as medical history of the mother (HCP 42.6% vs. patient 29.1%, $p < 0.001$) were reported more by HCPs.

Conclusions: Patients' reporting of demographic information and the medicinal product(s) tends to be more complete, whereas HCPs provide more complete information on timing of the exposure and clinical values such as details on the medical history of the mother. Insight into these differences may facilitate improvement of future pregnancy data collection and evaluation.

This study has been conducted with help of a master student of the study Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences at the University of Groningen.

Substudy 2a Creating and validating a dedicated assessment tool for measuring the quality of pregnancy data specifically (S2), part I, Elements to assess the quality of clinical information.

1. Yrea R J Van Rijt-Weetink, Khoezik Chamani, Toine C.G. Egberts, Florence P.A.M. Van Hunsel, David J Lewis, Laura M Yates, Ursula Winterfeld and Eugene P. Van Puijenbroek. Elements to Assess the Quality of Information of Case Reports in Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Data - a ConcePTION project. *Front. Drug Saf. Regul.*, 29 June 2023 Sec. Maternal-Fetal Medicine Volume 3 - 2023 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdsfr.2023.1187888>
2. This study has been published as a Master thesis at the University of Groningen.

Background: To assess the risk of exposure to a medicinal product during pregnancy in an individual case report, the necessary information should be present, complete and clearly described. Previously designed grading tools were not developed for pregnancy pharmacovigilance data.

Objective: This study aims to identify the elements that are necessary to assess of the quality of information for risk assessment of medicinal products used during pregnancy. This is a first step in the development of a validated method to assess the clinical quality of case reports in pregnancy pharmacovigilance data.

Methods: Potential information elements were determined by means of an expert focus group discussion and a survey based on its outcome. This provided an overview of possible information elements to be selected. For the final selection of the elements, a second survey and subsequent focus group discussion was used.

Results: Twenty-one information elements within seven categories were identified: information related to the association itself, the event, exposure to the medicinal product, maternal factors, pregnancy, labour, and the child.

Conclusions: This study identified elements considered necessary in the assessment of quality of information of case reports in pregnancy pharmacovigilance data, via an extensive four-step process.

This study has been conducted with help of a master student of the study Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences at the University of Groningen.

Substudy 2b Creating and validating a dedicated assessment tool for measuring the quality of pregnancy data specifically, part II, validation of the clinical assessment tool

1. A manuscript of the findings has been published: YRJ van Rijt-Weetink, ACG Egberts, FPAM van Hunsel, DJ Lewis, LM Yates, U Winterfeld, EP van Puijenbroek. Validation of a Novel Method to Assess the Clinical Quality of Information in Pregnancy-Related Pharmacovigilance Case Reports: A ConcePTION Project. *Drug Saf.* 2024 Mar;47(3):261-270. doi: 10.1007/s40264-023-01389-y. Epub 2024 Jan 6.
2. This study has been published as a Master thesis at the University of Groningen.

Background: To assess the causal relationship between a medicinal product and a reported event, relevant information needs to be present. Information elements for assessing cases of exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy were predefined and used in a new tool to assess the quality of information. However, the extent in which the presence or absence of these predefined information elements is associated with the overall clinical quality of these cases, as evaluated by pharmacovigilance experts, remains uncertain.

Objective: We aimed to validate a novel method to assess the clinical quality of information in real-world pregnancy pharmacovigilance case reports.

Methods: The clinical quality of case reports regarding medicinal product exposure and pregnancy-related outcomes was appraised from spontaneous reports, literature, Teratology Information Services (UK and Switzerland), The Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register, the Gilenya pregnancy registry and the Enhanced PV programme of Novartis. Assessment was done by means of the novel standardised tool based on the presence and relevance of information, and by expert judgement. The novel tool was compared to the expert assessment as the gold standard expressed as the area under the receiver operating characteristic curves, after which the sensitivity and specificity were calculated. Inter-rater variability was determined by means of weighted Cohen's kappa.

Results: One hundred and eighty-six case reports were included. The clinical quality score as assessed by the novel method was divided into three categories with cut-off values of 45% (poor to intermediate) and 65% (intermediate to excellent). Sensitivity was 0.93 and 0.96 for poor to intermediate and intermediate to excellent, respectively. Specificity was respectively 0.52 and 0.73. Inter-rater variability was 0.65 (95% confidence interval 0.53–0.78) for the newly developed approach, and 0.40 (95% confidence interval 0.28–0.52) for the gold standard assessment.

Conclusions: The tool described in this study using the presence and relevance of elements of information is the first designed, validated and standardised method for the assessment of the quality of information of case reports in pregnancy pharmacovigilance data. This method confers less inter-rater variability compared with a quality assessment by experts of pregnancy-related pharmacovigilance data.

This study has been conducted with help of a master student of the study Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences at the University of Groningen.

Substudy 3 Quality of Clinical Information in Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Data Sources – a contribution of the ConcePTION project

1. A manuscript of the findings has been published: YRJ van Rijt-Weetink, J van Gendt, ACG Egberts, FPAM van Hunsel, DJ Lewis, LM Yates, U Winterfeld, EP van Puijenbroek. Quality of Clinical Information in Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Data Sources – a contribution of the ConcePTION project. Submitted for publication July 2024
2. An abstract on this paper was presented at the 39th ICPE Halifax August 2023. Yrea R.J. van Rijt-Weetink, Jip van Gendt, Toine C.G. Egberts, Florence P.A.M. van Clinical Quality of Information of Primary Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Data Sources (Poster), Hunsel, David J. Lewis, Laura M. Yates, Ursula Winterfeld, Eugène P. van Puijenbroek.
3. This study has been published as a Master thesis at the University of Groningen.

Background: Good documentation of adverse events related to medicines is essential for assessment of safety signals. Information on the clinical quality of primary pregnancy safety data sources is lacking.

Objective: to assess the differences in clinical quality of various sources of primary pregnancy PV data.

Methods: Fifty reports of exposures to medicines during pregnancy were collected from: spontaneous and literature reports from EudraVigilance, European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS), the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register, enhanced PV programmes (EPV), and patient support programmes (PSP). Reports were standardized and anonymized, after which their clinical quality was assessed. Mean scores per source were compared using ANOVA (analysis of variance test).

Results: Mean clinical quality scores were 89.0% (SD 10.1%) for the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register, 77.1% (SD 13.3%) for TIS, 64.7% (SD 20.5%) for EPVs, 49.5% (SD 16.2%) for PSPs, 40.9% (SD 21.6%) for spontaneous reports, and 38.6% (SD 18.0%) for literature reports. All were statistically significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) except for spontaneous versus literature reports (mean difference 2.2%, $p = 0.99$) and spontaneous reports versus reports from PSPs (-8.6%, $p = 0.14$).

Conclusions: For data sources specifically designed for pregnancy data collection, the clinical quality of information generally outweighed sources designed to capture general safety information. EPV methods showed better scores for clinical quality compared to spontaneous reporting data for pregnancy PV.

This study has been conducted with help of a master student of the study Pharmacy at the University of Groningen.

Substudy 4 Pregnancy safety signals: regulatory decisions and implementation in daily practice

1. A manuscript of the findings will be submitted at a later stage.
2. This study has been published as a Master thesis at the University of Groningen.

Background: The timing of several aspects characterizing a pregnancy safety signal, e.g. first spontaneous report, first signal raised in literature, regulatory decision, TIS advice and publication of regulatory decisions in medical journals, and the differences in timing in respect to the nature of the regulatory decision taken is unknown.

Objective: to map the timing of teratological safety signals in clinical practice of licensed medicines in the Netherlands between 2002 and 2022.

Methods: Signals were extracted from the EPITT database. Subsequently, the marketing authorization date, EPITT submission date, date of the first discussion at EMA, regulatory decision date, date of implementation of the decision, publication date of the first report in literature, publication date of the first spontaneous report in VigiBase, publication of TIS advice and publication dates of articles in three major Dutch medical journals were noted. The mean and median time between the regulatory decision date ($t=0$) and all other relevant events were calculated. Boxplots were created to visualize the timing of events relative to the regulatory decision date.

Results: 22 signals were included in the study of which 7 were DHPC signals and 15 were SmPC signals. The mean drug age 27.2 years (median 25.2, range 1.4 – 58.4 years). The mean time for a signal to be discussed at EMA was 170.6 days (median 66, range 0-1482 days). The regulatory decision followed after a mean of 240.8 days (median 151, range 28-1732 days) after the occurrence of the signal. The mean time for a DHPC signal to be discussed was less compared to SmPC signals, 84.6 days vs. 186.3 days, respectively. In addition to that, the mean time between the filing date to EPITT and the date of the regulatory decision was also less for DHPC signals compared to SmPC signals, 218 days vs. 436.5 days. Publications in Dutch journals were sparse and mainly related to DHPC signals.

Conclusion: This study provides general information on the timing of aspects characterizing a safety signal. In general, the events occurred in the following consecutive order: spontaneous report – first publication in literature – TIS advice – regulatory decision made – dissemination in Dutch medical literature. This observation stresses the importance of the role TIS plays in providing information to healthcare providers. The mean time since marketing authorization of a medicinal product to being discussed as a teratological safety signal at EMA was 27,2 years. The decision to communicate a safety issue via a DHPC took the least amount of time. Publications in Dutch medical literature were mainly related to DHPC signals and most publications were found in PW.

This study has been conducted with help of the Dutch Medicines Evaluation board and a master student of the study Pharmacy at the University of Groningen.

sub-study 5 Cluster analysis of symptoms of Neurodevelopmental Delay associated with Valproate exposure during pregnancy

1. This study has been published as a Master thesis at the University of Groningen.
2. An abstract on this paper was presentation as a spotlight poster presentation at the 40th ICPE Berlin August 2024. D Gkolfi, F van Hunsel, Y van Rijt-Weetink, H Taavola, L Sandberg, B Raemaekers, DJ Lewis, LM Yates, EP van Puijenbroek. Changes in adverse event reporting of neurodevelopmental disorders after maternal valproate exposure, following scientific publications and regulatory signals, a contribution of the ConcePTION project.
3. This study will be submitted for publication in early 2025.

Background: Understanding how publications and regulations regarding neurodevelopmental disorders (NDD) and valproate (VPA) exposure during pregnancy affect the quantity and characteristics of Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs) submitted to pharmacovigilance centres is crucial for accurately interpreting quantitative approaches in signal detection.

Objective: To assess alterations in the outcome measures of signal detection methods, specifically disproportionality and clustering of events, subsequent to scientific publications and regulatory decisions concerning maternal VPA exposure and NDD in newborns.

Methods: Observational study in Vigibase, the WHO global database for potential side effects of medicines, using reports dated between January 1, 2000, and May 1, 2023. Changes in disproportionality and event clustering within ICSRs involving VPA exposure during pregnancy and NDD in newborns were studied, focusing in particular on significant events such as major publications and regulatory decisions by the EMA. Carbamazepine and lamotrigine, not associated with NDD, were used as controls in this research.

For VPA and events related to NDD, crude reporting odds ratios (ROR) and 95% confidence intervals were calculated. For cluster analysis the VigiGroup method was used, performing a repeated mixture-model-based cluster analysis using a latent class model for reports with conditionally independent binomial distributions for the reported events.

Clusters were randomised and assessed by three qualified assessors for reviewing and rating the meaningful clusters. Time trend graphs were used to visually study any changes in the reporting behaviour following the events that received public attention.

Results: The total number of pregnancy reports after the exclusions was 275.402 There was a clear increase of the number and diversity of reported NDD for VPA as compared to the controls. The most frequently reported event was autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Although one of the major scientific publications on VPA associated NDD seemed to have an impact on both the absolute number of reports and disproportionality, the effect of regulatory decisions was less clear. Cluster analysis showed a more diverse pattern of reported events over time.

Conclusions: Our study revealed a general increase in reporting and awareness of events related to NDD and VPA exposure during pregnancy and a more diverse way of reporting over time.

This study has been conducted on the database of the Uppsala Monitoring Centre with help of a master student of the study Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences at the University of Groningen.

Demonstration study 2.5.2 Primary and secondary safety data in multiple sclerosis patients -EU PAS 43370

The IMI ConcePTION project's Demonstration Study 2.5.2 addresses the need for standardised data in pregnancy drug safety research, as the current diversity in data formats and collection practices across regulatory, industry, academic, and clinical settings limits the comparability of findings and identification of safety signals. To overcome this, we developed a framework of Core Data Elements (CDEs) and a Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) to serve as the foundation for a standardised approach to data analysis. This approach was tested across a range of data providers, including pregnancy registries, two enhanced pharmacovigilance programs, and an ENTIS consortium of Teratology Information Services, with a focus on data related to medications used in treating multiple sclerosis. In the first phase of the study, the feasibility of mapping existing pregnancy exposure and outcome data to the standardised CDE definitions was assessed. The second phase further explored this by applying the common SAP to diverse data sources, enabling partner institutions to extract and map pregnancy safety data from their databases to the CDEs. Ultimately, 31 summary tables were generated, covering pregnancy details, maternal characteristics, risk factors, and outcomes. The SAP was subsequently used as the basis for a Delphi consensus study which produced a series of recommendations on the statistical analysis and reporting of single arm pregnancy medication safety studies. In a real-world validation, the methodology was also tested with the German MS Pregnancy Registry, an academic partner not initially involved in developing the study's methodology, demonstrating the robustness and adaptability of the standardised approach in diverse settings. The following sections present the titles and abstracts of publications resulting from this study.

Core data elements for pregnancy pharmacovigilance studies using primary source data collection methods: recommendations from the IMI ConcePTION project

A manuscript of the findings has been published: Jonathan L. Richardson, Alan Moore, Rebecca L. Bromley, Michael Stellfeld, Yvonne Geissbühler, Matthew Bluett-Duncan, Ursula Winterfeld, Guillaume Favre, Amalia Alexe, Alison M. Oliver, Yrea R. J. van Rijt-Weetink, Kenneth K. Hodson, Bitu Rezaallah, Eugene P. van Puijenbroek, David J. Lewis, Laura M. Yates. Core Data Elements for Pregnancy Pharmacovigilance Studies Using Primary Source Data Collection Methods: Recommendations from the IMI ConcePTION Project. *Drug Safety* (2023) 46:479–491. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40264-023-01291-7>

Background: The risks and benefits of medication use in pregnancy are typically established through postmarketing observational studies. As there is currently no standardised or systematic approach to the post-marketing assessment of medication safety in pregnancy, data generated through pregnancy pharmacovigilance (PregPV) research can be heterogenous and difficult to interpret.

Objective: The aim of this article is to describe the development of a reference framework of core data elements (CDEs) for collection in primary source PregPV studies that can be used to standardise data collection procedures and, thereby, improve data harmonisation and evidence synthesis capabilities.

Methods: This CDE reference framework was developed within the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) ConcePTION project by experts in pharmacovigilance, pharmacoepidemiology, medical statistics, risk–benefit communication, clinical teratology, reproductive toxicology, genetics, obstetrics, paediatrics, and child psychology. The framework was produced through a scoping review of data collection systems used by established PregPV datasets, followed by extensive discussion

and debate around the value, definition, and derivation of each data item identified from these systems.

Results: The finalised listing of CDEs comprises 98 individual data elements, arranged into 14 tables of related fields. These data elements are openly available on the European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) website (<http://www.entsi-org.eu/cde>).

Conclusion: With this set of recommendations, we aim to standardise PregPV primary source data collection processes to improve the speed at which high-quality evidence-based statements can be provided about the safety of medication use in pregnancy.

Delphi method consensus on statistical analysis and reporting recommendations for single arm pregnancy medication safety studies investigating pregnancy, birth and neonatal health outcomes; a contribution from IMI-ConcePTION

A manuscript of this work was submitted for publication in October 2024 (currently under peer review with Drug Safety).

Background and Objective: Standardisation of current approaches to safety monitoring of medications used in pregnancy is lacking. As a result, it often takes years or decades to provide the quality and quantity of data which are needed to reliably inform on the risks and benefits of gestational medication use. Introducing standardised procedures for data collection, analysis and reporting may help improve data quality and the speed of data generation. The objective of this study is to provide a series of recommendations on the statistical analysis and reporting of single arm pregnancy medication safety studies.

Methods: A Delphi study was undertaken to acquire consensus agreement on recommendations from experts with extensive knowledge and experience in conducting pregnancy drug safety studies. Preliminary recommendations were adapted from a statistical analysis plan developed within ConcePTION to standardise and optimise the analysis of data from various medication in pregnancy safety sources. These recommendations, along with their scientific justification and examples of how to calculate and describe exposure and outcome incidences, were subsequently critiqued and improved through a series of Delphi review rounds which allowed the expert panel to provide open but anonymised feedback. As a final step, agreement to inclusion scoring was assessed using a five-point Likert scale.

Results: The recommendations were produced with the input of 20 experts from nine countries. The methodology applied in this study produced a set of 30 recommendations spread over five themes. These included descriptions of: (i) the study sample, (ii) medication exposure; (iii) maternal outcomes; (iv) pregnancy and birth outcomes; and (v) fetal and neonatal outcomes. Of the 30 recommendations, 19 were strongly advised while 11 were included for consideration where implementation may be beneficial for supplementing data communication. The final set of recommendations all scored highly on the Likert scale (median score 5, IQR 4 to 5), with a high proportion of the expert review panel scoring the recommendations ≥ 4 ($n=420/448$, 93.8%, 95% CI; 90.9 to 95.7%).

Conclusion: Use of the finalised set of recommendations as a framework for designing statistical analysis and data reporting plans should be encouraged to help standardise published evidence around medication use in pregnancy.

Improving Data Collection in Pregnancy Safety Studies: Towards Standardisation of Data Elements in Pregnancy Reports from Public and Private Partners, A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project

1. A manuscript of the findings has been published: Guillaume Favre, Jonathan L. Richardson, Alan Moore, Yvonne Geissbühler, Valentine Jehl, Alison Oliver, Svetlana Shechtman, Orna Diav-Citrin, Maya Berlin, Tal De Haan, David Baud, Alice Panchaud, Anil Mor, Meritxell Sabidó, Sabrina de Souza, Christina Chambers, Yrea R. J. van Rijt-Weetink, Eugène P. van Puijenbroek, Laura M. Yates, François Girardin, Michael Stellfeld*, Ursula Winterfeld*. * The authors contributed equally. Improving Data Collection in Pregnancy Safety Studies: Towards Standardisation of Data Elements in Pregnancy Reports from Public and Private Partners, A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project. *Drug Safety* (2024) 47:227–236. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40264-023-01384-3>
2. An abstract of this paper was presented at the SGAIM Frühjahrskongress 2023, 10.5 - 12.5.2023, Basel as a Poster. G. Favre, J.L. Richardson, G. Yvonne, V. Jehl, A. Oliver, S. Shechtman, O. Diav-Citrin, M. Berlin, A. Mor, M. Sabido, C. Chambers, Y.R. van Rijt Weetink, E.P. van Puijenbroek, L.M. Yates, T. Buclin, M. Stellfeld*, U. Winterfeld*. * The authors contributed equally. Improving Data Collection in Pregnancy Safety Studies: Towards Standardisation of Data Elements in Pregnancy Reports from Public and Private Partners, A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project.
3. An abstract of this paper was presented at the 34th annual ENTIS meeting 2023, 31.8 - 2.9.2023, Dublin as a poster. G. Favre, J.L. Richardson, G. Yvonne, V. Jehl, A. Oliver, S. Shechtman, O. Diav-Citrin, M. Berlin, A. Mor, M. Sabido, C. Chambers, Y.R. van Rijt Weetink, E.P. van Puijenbroek, L.M. Yates, T. Buclin, M. Stellfeld*, U. Winterfeld*. * The authors contributed equally. Improving Data Collection in Pregnancy Safety Studies: Towards Standardisation of Data Elements in Pregnancy Reports from Public and Private Partners, A Contribution from the ConcePTION Project.

Introduction and Objective: The ConcePTION project aims to improve the way medication use during pregnancy is studied. This includes exploring the possibility of developing a distributed data processing and analysis infrastructure using a common data model that could form a foundational platform for future surveillance and research. A prerequisite would be that data from various data access providers (DAPs) can be harmonised according to an agreed set of standard rules concerning the structure and content of the data. To do so, a reference framework of core data elements (CDEs) recommended for primary data studies on drug safety during pregnancy was previously developed. The aim of this study was to assess the ability of several public and private DAPs using different primary data sources focusing on multiple sclerosis, as a pilot, to map their respective data variables and definitions with the CDE recommendations framework.

Methods: Four pregnancy registries (Gilenya, Novartis; Aubagio, Sanofi; the Organization of Teratology Information Specialists [OTIS]; Aubagio, Sanofi; the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register, Lareb), two enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes (Gilenya PRIM, Novartis; MAPLE-MS, Merck Healthcare KGaA) and four Teratology Information Services (UK TIS, Jerusalem TIS, Zerifin TIS, Swiss TIS) participated in the study. The ConcePTION primary data source CDE includes 51 items covering administrative functions, the description of pregnancy, maternal medical history, maternal illnesses arising in pregnancy, delivery details, and pregnancy and infant outcomes. For each variable in the CDE, the DAPs identified whether their variables were: identical to the one mentioned in the CDE; derived; similar but with a divergent definition; or not available.

Results: The majority of the DAP data variables were either directly taken (85%, n = 305/357, range 73–94% between DAPs) or derived by combining different variables (12%, n = 42/357, range 0–24% between DAPs) to conform to the CDE variables and definitions. For very few of the DAP variables, alignment with the CDE items was not possible, either because of divergent definitions (1%, n = 3/357, range 0–2% between DAPs) or because the variables were not available (2%, n = 7/357, range 0–4% between DAPs).

Conclusions: Data access providers participating in this study presented a very high proportion of variables matching the CDE items, indicating that alignment of definitions and harmonisation of data analysis by different stakeholders to accelerate and strengthen pregnancy pharmacovigilance safety data analyses could be feasible.

Improving data harmonisation in pregnancy safety studies: evaluating the feasibility of standardised data analysis of pregnancy reports from public and private partners, a contribution from the ConcePTION project.

1. A manuscript of this work has been submitted for publication to Drug Safety.
2. An abstract of this paper was presented at the ENTIS-OTIS meeting 2024, 12.9 - 15.9.2024, Nyborg as a poster. Ursula Winterfeld, Guillaume Favre, Jonathan Richardson, Alan Moore, Yvonne Geissbühler, Valentine Jehl, Lisa Prach, Alison Oliver, Svetlana Shechtman, Orna Diav-Citrin O, Maya Berlin M, David Baud D, Alice Panchaud A, Anil Mor, Meritxell Sabido, Sabrina de Souza, Christina Chambers C, Yrea van Rijt-Weetink, Eugène van Puijenbroek, Laura Yates, François Girardin F, Michael Stellfeld. Improving data collection in pregnancy safety studies: evaluating the feasibility of standardised data analysis of pregnancy reports from public and private partners, a contribution from the ConcePTION project.

Introduction: Aligned with the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI) ConcePTION project's goal of advancing drug safety research in pregnancy, we explored the feasibility of employing a standardised list of Core Data Elements (CDE) and statistical outputs to harmonise data collection and analysis from various study partners.

Methods: Study partners from public institutions and pharmaceutical companies extracted pregnancy safety data from their databases and mapped them as best as possible with the Core Data Elements (CDE) defined in the context of the IMI ConcePTION project. They then analysed the datasets using a common statistical analysis plan to create 31 summary tables covering pregnancy details, maternal characteristics, risk factors, and outcomes. In addition, to further understand the potential difficulties/challenges faced by the data access providers (DAP), contextual information including type of data collection in place, initially applied definition or format of variables were collected via questionnaires. These were essential to evaluate the possible limitations of the proposed approach.

Results: We found a high level of completion for the summary data tables for case attrition and disposition, maternal demographics timing of exposure, pregnancy outcomes, malformation type, and malformation prevalence. All partners provided complete tables on timing of exposure and pregnancy outcomes. However, due to the original data collection tool in place and the granularity of data collected, three DAPs could not apply the recommended definition of a prospectively-reported pregnancy and two could not apply the recommended approach for categorising congenital malformation as per EUROCAT guidelines. This resulted in the poor completion of the table describing "Prevalence of major malformation by timing of exposure using the recommended simple definition for prospective" by these DAPs.

Conclusions: While this study demonstrates the feasibility of mapping to CDE and standardising the analytic approach to describe pregnancy exposure and outcome from several data partners, it also

**Demonstration study 2.5.3 LifeTIME study focusing on
neurodevelopmental delay -EU PAS 43300-43376**

Demonstration study 2.5.4 TeratoPHEN

Demonstration study 2.5.5 Validation of primary source pregnancy pharmacovigilance data -EU PAS 44505

A variety of data collection techniques are utilised in pregnancy pharmacovigilance research, with self-reported information included in many, often for data collection efficiency reasons. However, data on the validity of self-reported information is often questioned. The development of routine long-term surveillance systems and research tools for use in pregnancy pharmacovigilance is paramount for decreasing the data gaps which exist around the childhood health and development impacts of in utero medication exposure. Due to high costs and participant time requirements, wide-scale implementation of routine clinical assessments of childhood health and development for all medications where there may be developmental concerns are generally considered infeasible. However, the development and implementation of a set of routine childhood health and development screening questionnaires, for routine completion by parents of children with prenatal medication exposure, could provide a valuable data source for long-term pregnancy pharmacovigilance.

Demonstration project 2.5.3 was performed to investigate the feasibility of utilising existing pregnancy cohorts and safety monitoring systems to operate a bespoke, online data collection tool, for the purpose of collecting parental/care giver reports of longer-term infant health and development outcome data. Demonstration project 2.5.5 focused on the validation of the parent/care giver reported data. The original plan for demonstration project 2.5.5 was to undertake two sub-studies, with the first focussing on validation testing of primary source pregnancy exposure and outcomes (Novartis pharmacovigilance data, with subsequent comparison with a paired report from a healthcare professional. During the feasibility testing phase of this sub-study it was identified that there was a lack of paired parent/care giver and healthcare professional jointly reported data within the Novartis pharmacovigilance data system to allow for a validation analysis to be performed. The second sub-study focussed on comparing results of face-to-face clinical reviews and neuropsychological assessments with the data generated by the caregiver-report questionnaire set, either via the online data collection tool or paper questionnaires. This validation was performed to assess the suitability of the questionnaire set for collecting the data required for child health, dysmorphology and neurodevelopmental outcome screening, and thereby provide insight into whether this tool could be used for large-scale implementation in future pregnancy pharmacovigilance systems. This was conducted in two sub-studies, publication outputs from which are detailed in the following sections:

Sub study 1: Validation of neurodevelopmental data

- A preliminary validation analysis of neurodevelopmental data has been completed and results were presented at the 4th Joint ENTIS-OTIS Conference, September 12th–15th 2024, Nyborg, Denmark (*Developing a caregiver reported questionnaire set for neurodevelopmental outcomes in school-aged children for pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance: A contribution from the ConcePTION project* - Matthew Bluett-Duncan, Rebecca L. Bromley, Elizabeth Heslop, Laura M. Yates, Jonathan L. Richardson).
- Following final analyses the study will be submitted for publication in early 2025.

The results of this validation indicate that the questionnaire used in demonstration project 2.5.3 are likely sufficient to detect signals of neuroteratogenic insult. Future work is required to further develop and optimise a battery of parent/care-giver completed questionnaires that can be used to assess in utero medication exposure and school aged neurodevelopmental functioning.

Meeting Abstract (4th Joint ENTIS-OTIS Conference, September 12th–15th 2024, Nyborg, Denmark) – Developing a caregiver reported questionnaire set for neurodevelopmental outcomes in school-aged children for pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance: A contribution from the ConcePTION project

Matthew Bluett-Duncan, Rebecca L. Bromley, Elizabeth Heslop, Laura M. Yates, Jonathan L. Richardson

Introduction: The assessment of neurodevelopmental outcomes in children and young adults exposed

to teratogenic medications during pregnancy is increasingly recognised as an essential element of pregnancy pharmacovigilance. However, direct assessments of neurodevelopment are costly, time-consuming and require expertise that may not always be available. We report preliminary findings regarding the utility of caregiver-reported questionnaires in screening for negative neurodevelopmental outcomes in school age children and adults. The preliminary analysis focuses primarily on the validation of the PROMIS – Perceived Cognitive Functioning (PROMIS-PCF). This measure consists of 43 items measuring everyday cognitive functioning and was designed to screen for paediatric neurotoxicity but is yet to be tested in the context of fetal exposures.

Methods: We report findings from two studies to demonstrate the validity of the PROMIS-PCF. **Study 1:** Parents of individuals with and without a diagnosis of Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder (FVSD) (n = 147, 7-37 years) completed the PROMIS-PCF questionnaire. **Study 2:** Parents of individuals with confirmed or suspected fetal exposure syndromes were recruited to take part in the neurodevelopmental assessments (n = 47, 5-16 years). Trained researchers administered a battery of neuropsychological assessments, including the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children – 5th Edition (WISC-V), and caregivers completed a series of questionnaires, including the PROMIS-PCF and the Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function – 2nd Edition (BRIEF-2).

Results: Study 1 demonstrated that the PROMIS-PCF was able to detect significant expected differences in cognitive functioning between those with a diagnosis of FVSD (n = 99, M = 38.5, SD = 10.2), those exposed to valproate but without a diagnosis of FVSD (n = 22, M = 47.1, SD = 11.2) and those not exposed to valproate at all (n = 23, M = 48.3, SD = 9.5). In study 2, when using the standard cut-off for suspected cognitive impairment in the PROMIS-PCF (<40), agreement with research-administered WISC-V demonstrated good sensitivity for severe disruptions to cognitive functioning (Sensitivity = 91.7%). Specificity was low however (Specificity = 36.8%). Due to the high level of impairment observed in this sample, the standard cut-offs may have been inappropriate. Therefore, we adjusted the cut-off based on the current data (<36) and saw a substantial improvement to specificity (sensitivity = 79.2%, specificity = 63.2%). Specificity was likely further impacted due to the PROMIS-PCF detecting memory and attentional difficulties which are not directly measured by the WISC-V. To explore this, we performed a comparison of the PROMIS-PCF and the BRIEF-2, which are more closely aligned with each other. This analysis showed excellent sensitivity (91.9%) and specificity (85.7%). Other caregiver-reported questionnaires revealed significant difficulties experienced by individuals with FES across a range of domains, including sensory processing and psychosocial functioning, both of which are challenging to assess in the time-limited and artificial setting of a researcher-led assessment

Conclusions: The study finds that the PROMIS-PCF is an efficient and flexible tool for large-scale neurodevelopmental surveillance. It is sensitive to identify severe disruptions to cognitive functioning and is able to detect expected differences between teratogen-exposed and non-exposed groups. It also appears to be a viable proxy for the longer and more expensive BRIEF-2. However, it detects a higher rate of moderate disruption than the WISC-V, which is likely due to a misalignment of the cognitive domains being assessed and may partially be a product of the current high-risk sample. Further validation work is planned that includes a larger, lower-risk sample. This will allow for a more robust assessment of the tool's applicability to a broader population with a wider range of strengths and difficulties, improving the robustness of our results and further investigating specificity. Further analysis of the existing data will now be carried out ascertain the validity and utility of the full neurodevelopmental questionnaire set.

Sub study 2: Validation of child health data

At the time of publishing this report, the validation of childhood health data has not been completed. Within the study, 60 participants completed an online questionnaire to collect information about infant health, the results of which have been written into a publication which will shortly be submitted for peer review (details in abstract below). Forty-eight women accepted an invite to a telephone clinical review performed by a clinical geneticist, and these have been performed. In sub-study 2, we will compare the results of the clinical review (for completeness and accuracy) with the information that was self-volunteered by the study participants via the questionnaire. Agreement between parental reports and clinical assessment results will be quantified using a range of appropriate statistical approaches, including Cohen's Kappa statistic, correlation coefficients and calculations of sensitivity/specificity. Descriptive statistics and qualitative methods will also be utilised. From early informal review of the

data collected in the clinical reviews, it is anticipated that the findings of this validation study will demonstrate that the questionnaire was sufficient at collecting the required level of detail about prenatal medication use and childhood health complications.

Study manuscript (to be submitted for peer review): Impact of sodium valproate exposure in utero on longer term health: an observational study and a contribution from the ConcePTION project

Patricia Wells, Matthew Bluett-Duncan, Rebecca L. Bromley, Laura M. Yates, Jonathan L. Richardson

Objective: In the UK, 20,000 people are estimated to have been affected by exposure to sodium valproate (VPA) in utero. While congenital malformations and neurodevelopmental impairments are well-described in this patient group limited data are available for impact on physical health. We aim to document the physical health outcomes in a cohort of individuals exposed to sodium valproate (VPA) in utero and their unexposed siblings.

Methods: This cross-sectional, observational study, collected primary data via questionnaire from primary care-givers of individuals exposed to VPA in utero, and siblings not exposed to VPA in utero. Details regarding maternal health and pregnancy, as well as offspring health and neurodevelopmental outcomes was collected. Participants were recruited from the UK, Ireland, New Zealand and Australia. Reported physical health of those exposed to VPA monotherapy in utero was compared to that of unexposed siblings.

Results: Health concerns were reported in a median of 8 of 18 study categories for those with a formal diagnosis of fetal valproate spectrum disorder (FVSD). a. In the VPA exposed group without a formal FVSD diagnosis the median was 5 and 1.5 in the non-exposed group. Health concerns in VPA exposed group were more common and met statistical significance for: neonatal unit admission, back pain, bladder and bowel difficulties, oral health concerns, joint hypermobility, respiratory diagnosis, dietary requirements and ear infections.

Conclusions: This study highlights the significant burden of challenging physical health concerns in those exposed to VPA in utero which significantly impact on quality of life and in some instances, persist into adulthood.

List of abbreviations

ADR	Adverse Drug Reaction
CDE	Core Data Element
CDM	Common Data Model
DAP	Data Access Provider
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ENTIS	European Network of Teratology Information Services
EPV	Enhanced Pharmacovigilance programme
FES	Fetal Exposure Syndrome
FVSD	Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder
HCP	Healthcare professional
ICSR	Individual Case Safety Report
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
MAH	Marketing Authorization Holder
MS	Multiple sclerosis
NA	Not applicable
NDD	Neurodevelopmental Disorders
OTIS	Organization of Teratology Information Specialists
PregPV	Pregnancy pharmacovigilance
PSP	Patient Support Programme
SD	Standard Deviation
SAP	Statistical Analysis Plan
SRS	Spontaneous Reporting System
TIS	Teratology Information Service
UKTIS	United Kingdom Teratology Information Service
VPA	Valproic acid
WP	Work package

References

1. Lupattelli A, Spigset O, Twigg MJ, et al. Medication use in pregnancy: a cross-sectional, multinational web-based study. *BMJ Open* 2014;4(2):e004365. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2013-004365 [published Online First: 2014/02/19]
2. Mitchell AA, Gilboa SM, Werler MM, et al. Medication use during pregnancy, with particular focus on prescription drugs: 1976-2008. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2011;205(1):51 e1-8. doi: 10.1016/j.ajog.2011.02.029 [published Online First: 2011/04/26]
3. ConcePTION full proposal. 2018
4. Adam MP, Polifka JE, Friedman JM. Evolving knowledge of the teratogenicity of medications in human pregnancy. *American Journal of Medical Genetics Part C: Seminars in Medical Genetics* 2011;157(3):175-82. doi: 10.1002/ajmg.c.30313
5. EMA. ICH guideline E2B (R3) on electronic transmission of individual case safety reports (ICSRs) - data elements and message specification - implementation guide, 2013.
6. Lester J, Neyarapally GA, Lipowski E, et al. Evaluation of FDA safety-related drug label changes in 2010. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf* 2013;22(3):302-5. doi: 10.1002/pds.3395 [published Online First: 2013/01/03]
7. Raine JM. Risk management - a European regulatory view. New York: Wiley 2007.
8. Scholl JHG, van Hunsel F, Hak E, et al. A prediction model-based algorithm for computer-assisted database screening of adverse drug reactions in the Netherlands. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf* 2018;27(2):199-205. doi: 10.1002/pds.4364 [published Online First: 2017/12/23]
9. Candore G, Juhlin K, Manlik K, et al. Comparison of statistical signal detection methods within and across spontaneous reporting databases. *Drug Saf* 2015;38(6):577-87. doi: 10.1007/s40264-015-0289-5 [published Online First: 2015/04/23]
10. van Puijenbroek EP, Bate A, Leufkens HG, et al. A comparison of measures of disproportionality for signal detection in spontaneous reporting systems for adverse drug reactions. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf* 2002;11(1):3-10. doi: 10.1002/pds.668 [published Online First: 2002/05/10]
11. Bergvall T, Noren GN, Lindquist M. vigiGrade: a tool to identify well-documented individual case reports and highlight systematic data quality issues. *Drug Saf* 2014;37(1):65-77. doi: 10.1007/s40264-013-0131-x [published Online First: 2013/12/18]
12. Oosterhuis I, Rolfes L, Ekhardt C, et al. First experiences with a tool to measure the level of clinical information present in adverse drug reaction reports. *Expert Opinion on Drug Safety* 2017;17(2):111-15. doi: 10.1080/14740338.2018.1400008